

S3E Experts

Call for Expression of Interest #02

OPENING:

START AND CHARGE: 16 October 2023 (12:00 CET)

REVERSE: 15 November 2023 (12:00 CET)

CLOSING:

START AND CHARGE: 30 November 2023 (17:00 CET)

REVERSE: 15 January 2024 (17:00 CET)

Disclaimer

The information, documentation, and figures available in this document are provided by the S3E project's consortium under EC grant agreement **101072135** and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Copyright notice

© S3E 2022-2025

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
v0.1	25-09-2023	Update document #1	HST
v0.2	01-10-2023	Upload Charge Dates	EPLO
v0.3	06-10-2023	Upload Reverse Dates	IDI
v0.4	06-10-2023	Final Review	HST

Table of Contents

1	The S3E Project	4
1.1.	The S3E Structure.....	5
2	Open Call for Experts	6
3	S3E Expert	7
3.1.	Tasks for each Role	7
3.1.1.	S3E Evaluators (S3E Start, S3E Charge)	7
3.1.2.	S3E Mentors for Deep Tech Projects (S3E Start).....	8
3.1.3.	Mentors for Deep Tech Growth Startups (S3E Charge)	8
3.1.4.	Deep Tech Brokers (S3E Reverse).....	8
3.2.	Workload and Schedule.....	9
3.2.1.	S3E Evaluators (S3E Start, S3E Charge)	9
3.2.2.	S3E Mentors for Deep Tech Projects (S3E Start).....	9
3.2.3.	Mentors for Deep Tech Growth Startups (S3E Charge)	10
3.2.4.	3.2.4. Deep Tech Brokers (S3E Reverse).....	10
3.3.	Working as an S3E expert	11
3.3.1.	Place of Work.....	11
3.3.2.	Conflict of Interest.....	11
3.3.3.	Confidentiality.....	11
3.3.4.	Remuneration.....	11
4	Application and Selection Process	11
4.1.	Open Call Submission.....	11
4.2.	Eligible Profiles.....	12
4.3.	Exclusion	12
4.4.	Selection.....	13
4.5.	Experts Assignment	13
4.6.	Contracting.....	13
5	Benefits for all Experts	13
6	Other Conditions	14
6.1.	Ownership and Use of Results	14
6.2.	Data Protection	14

1 The S3E Project

Southern Europe Entrepreneurship Engine or **S3E** is an EU-funded project under the European Innovation Ecosystem initiative of Horizon Europe¹. We aim to improve the market connectedness and efficiency of research teams, startups & SMEs working on Deep Tech. The core of the S3E activities is the implementation of an **Engine Programme** that will offer innovation support services to Research Teams, Technology Transfer Officers (TTOs) and start-ups at various stages of their growth journey.

The S3E programme **mission** is to accelerate Deep Tech projects coming from research teams, and deep tech solutions coming from start-ups and SMEs that can impact social development and economic growth for a more sustainable future.

The **goal** of S3E is to reduce the market risk for Southern Europe Deep Tech companies in their struggle to secure funding and reach the market. The programme focuses on:

- 1 Upskilling researchers to an **entrepreneurship mindset**.
- 2 Supporting growth-stage startups in **business development**.
- 3 **Brokering** access to investment.
- 4 Facilitating **Open Innovation** with Industry partners.
- 5 Contributing to the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**.

The S3E project **vision** is to develop an **engine of growth** that will contribute to improving the connectedness and efficiency of **entrepreneurship ecosystems in Southern European countries**.

S3E consortium partners are:

- **HiSeedTech** - A not-for-profit association founded by private companies that came together with the purpose of enabling the creation of value from knowledge through technology entrepreneurship and open innovation.
- **EPLO Institute for Sustainable Development** – part of an international organization dedicated to mainstreaming the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the EU Green Deal, providing capacity building, policy work and educational programs.
- **IDI** (International Development Ireland) specializes in practical day-to-day implementation for Government agencies in economies which are growing and changing rapidly.
- **Australo** Interinnov Marketing Lab SI - is a marketing agency specializing in growth hacking for research and innovation.

¹ Grant agreement ID: 101072135 ([see here the Cordis fact sheet](#))

1.1. The S3E Structure

S3E focuses on accelerating **deep tech projects, start-ups, and SMEs** that, by providing solutions towards a more sustainable society and economy, can impact social development and economic growth in these countries and contribute to the timely achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, in line with the EU Green Deal, the Recovery and Resilience Facility and the Next Generation EU Fund. S3E provides skills to **researchers and technology transfer officers** in science-based entrepreneurship and technology commercialization. The S3E also supports **growth-stage start-ups** in business development and raising investment and provides technology brokerage for corporates and **scale-up stage start-ups and SMEs**.

The programme is built around **three tracks** of bespoke services tailored to start-ups' varying levels of maturity (i.e., early, growth, and scaling stages):

Figure 1. S3E Tracks

- **S3E Start:** For research teams and technology transfer officers, S3E offers a hands-on training programme to explore the potential social and economic impact of their scientific discoveries.
- **S3E Charge:** For growth start-ups, S3E provides mentoring and networking to develop an investment-ready business plan and facilitates access to non-dilutable and dilutable funding.
- **S3E Reverse:** For scaling start-ups and SMEs, S3E will set up an Open Innovation ecosystem to broker, connect and match corporates to scaling start-ups through a challenge-solution duality.

2 Open Call for Experts

The S3E programme is seeking external experts to support its second open call for the three tracks (Start, Charge, Reverse). As an expert, you can play a crucial role in various aspects of the programme, including evaluation of proposals, mentorship, business advice, and matching and brokering. The current document is meant to set up the **call for expression of interest for experts to support the S3E programme** on its second open call for the three tracks (**Start, Charge, Reverse**).

Roles and Tasks for Experts

- **Evaluators:** Responsible for evaluating proposals submitted by research teams, and growth start-ups for the **S3E Start** and **S3E Charge** Programs.
- **Mentors for deep tech projects:** Guide research teams on developing a business case for a product, service, or process grounded on a technology proposed within the **S3E Start** Programme.
- **Mentors for deep tech growth startups:** Assist the startups in developing an investment-ready business plan within the **S3E Charge** Programme.
- **Deep tech brokers:** Match corporate challenges with the solutions provided by startups or SME in the **S3E Reverse** Programme.

Depending on the type of experts, your tasks will have a specific duration:

- **Evaluators S3E Start:** 12 January - 26 January 2024
- **Evaluators S3E Charge:** 18 December 2023 - 8 January 8, 2024
- **Mentors for deep tech projects (S3E Start):** 6 February - 6 June 2024
- **Mentors for deep tech growth startups (S3E Charge):** 18 January - April 26 2024
- **Deep tech brokers (S3E Reverse):** 1 April - 30 September 2024

Experts will have to perform this work and provide services as independent individuals and **NOT** represent a company or organization. See what is expected from you on point 3.

Application is a mandatory prerequisite to work as an expert in the S3E programme. Application does not automatically mean that the experts will be joining the programme. This will depend on the project needs and fulfillment of certain formal requirements. When experts are assigned to any of the described roles, they will need to sign a contract and a non-disclosure agreement. The application form is available at <https://www.f6s.com/s3e-call-for-experts/apply>.

You can check the final outcomes of the programme by going to our YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@south3e618/>).

3 S3E Expert

3.1. Tasks for each Role

S3E involve different types of independent experts to assist in the implementation, evaluation, and monitoring of the programme. These include:

- **S3E Evaluators (S3E Start, S3E Charge)**
- **S3E Start Mentors for deep tech projects (S3E Start)**
- **S3E Charge Mentors for deep tech growth startups (S3E Charge)**
- **S3E Deep tech brokers (S3E Reverse)**

3.1.1. S3E Evaluators (S3E Start, S3E Charge)

The **S3E Evaluators** will select the research teams, technology transfer officers, and growth startups that will join the **S3E Start** and **S3E Charge**, respectively.

On the **S3E Start** the evaluators will receive the application forms from **research teams** and rank them according to the following criteria:

- **Technology uniqueness:** technologies that are “deep” enough to show unique features and competitiveness on a global basis have certain characteristics that allow them to be protected (e.g., by a patent).
- **Technology breadth:** technologies that are “broad” enough to support a range of product possibilities (i.e., platform technologies).
- **Global market size and reach:** the commercial potential of the products, services or processes that can be generated from the technologies, that is, the potential of the technologies to generate products or services for large global markets and for clearly identifiable customers.
- **Team motivation:** motivation to participate in the training programme and the entrepreneurial spirit of the team, perceived from the application form.

On the **S3E Charge**, the evaluators will receive the application forms and need to rank them according to a set of detailed criteria related: to the sustainability of the economic opportunity resulting from the match between the technology and the market and the perception of the motivation of the team to participate in the programme. The pitch and the written business case along with the alignment to the UN SDGs will also carry significant value during the evaluation process.

A guideline to evaluate the applications and an evaluation grid will be provided to all the S3E evaluators to complete the evaluation process. Additionally, a kick-off meeting will be

booked to provide all the needed information to grant a transparent and smooth evaluation process.

3.1.2. S3E Mentors for Deep Tech Projects (S3E Start)

The **S3E Mentors for deep tech projects** will guide research teams on developing a business case for a product, service or process and a pitch deck of the project, both grounded on the technology proposed to S3E Start. It is important to note that the approach used in the programme will be highly iterative in the sense that as the teams amass information from the market, they may be required to iterate back to improve previous decisions and findings. The role of the mentors is crucial in this iterative process in forcing the teams to iterate back and select the best opportunities.

3.1.3. Mentors for Deep Tech Growth Startups (S3E Charge)

The **S3E Mentors for deep tech growth startups** will guide the startups on developing an investment-ready business plan, to be delivered as the outcome of the programme. The business plan will build upon the business case provided by the participating teams on the application form and shall include detailed sections on: (i) opportunity description, (ii) product concept, (iii) technology, IP and pipeline, (iv) market analysis, (v) strategic framework, (vi) sales plan and marketing, (vii) development roadmap, (viii) financials and (ix) team. Exchanging experiences and network of contacts are expected.

The mentors for deep tech projects (3.1.2) and deep tech growth startups (3.1.3) will have a mentoring handbook outlining the main pillars of the mentoring process, to ensure that each participating research team and start-up receive high-quality mentoring in accordance with the vision of the S3E project. Additionally, a kick-off meeting will be booked to provide all the needed information needed to support both programs.

3.1.4. Deep Tech Brokers (S3E Reverse)

The role of S3E deep tech brokers is to analyze the challenges posed by corporates that require relevant field of expertise, interview the liaison element of the corporate for a better understanding of the challenge and fine-tune its specification, analyze and interview scale start-ups that match their field(s) of expertise, choose the adequate solution provider and broker the contacts between the corporate and the start-up(s) that may have a solution to solve the challenge.

3.2. Workload and Schedule

The amount of work and schedule depends on the role to be performed:

3.2.1. S3E Evaluators (S3E Start, S3E Charge)

On the evaluation of deep tech projects and growth startups proposals applying, it is expected that **evaluators will be available to do the selection on the following periods:**

- Evaluators **S3E Start**: 12 January – 26 January 2024
- Evaluators **S3E Charge**: 18 December 2023 – 8 January 8, 2024

The evaluation process will be composed of two stages:

- First, the application will be assessed by S3E project partners to validate if it conforms to the eligibility criteria of **S3E Start** and **S3E Charge**.
- Second, the application will be assessed by the evaluators.

We will provide a guideline to evaluate the proposals and an evaluation grid. Each evaluator will be signed with a maximum of five applications that will correspond to an **amount of work of approximately eight hours**.

3.2.2. S3E Mentors for Deep Tech Projects (S3E Start)

On mentoring deep tech projects, mentors are expected to meet with the research teams eight times in a **1.5-hour meeting in a period of 3 months**. The S3E team will try to assign each mentor to a team from the same country to avoid major time differences. Besides that, it is expected that mentors will be available for a briefing and debriefing meeting with the S3E team and to be present at the open day of the programme that will be held on the 6 of June 2024. The meetings will be held online and the first will be on the 8 of February. The remaining meetings will be scheduled by the mentors and the teams between the following days:

February	March	April	May
8	6-8	2-5	8-10
21-23	20-22	24-26	22-24

Table 1. Schedule of S3E Start mentors.

3.2.3. Mentors for Deep Tech Growth Startups (S3E Charge)

Mentors for deep tech growth projects (S3E Charge) are expected to **have seven-hour-long meetings during a 14-week period** with the start-up they have been designated to assist in developing an investment-ready business plan. Each mentor is assigned one start-up team for the S3E Charge programme. It is expected that mentors are available for a briefing and debriefing meeting with the S3E team and to assist with the open day of the programme that will be held at the end of April 2024. The meetings will be held online on the following dates (there is flexibility on the date as long as it takes place within that specific week).

January	February	March	April
22-26	5-9	4-8	1-5
	19-23	18-22	15-19

Table 2. Schedule of S3E Charge Mentors

3.2.4. 3.2.4. Deep Tech Brokers (S3E Reverse)

Technology Brokers are professionals that can bridge the gap between research and industry. They are intermediaries and mediators between science and industry. They have a deep understanding of the R&I process and can understand the challenges that today's organisations, public and private, face. They have product and/or project management experience and the technical background to break down problems and ask the right questions. They are experienced experts and specialists in their scientific fields but at the same time they have a broad understanding of innovation processes. Their job will be to help the Challenge Organisations better define their challenge and develop a set of solid technical specifications that will help the scale-ups design the best solutions for them. Through our technology brokerage process, the organizations will be able to better define their problems and needs and find potential solutions through their collaboration with a smaller innovative company. Deep Tech Brokers selected for our programme are expected to dedicate around **10 hours in private consultations and meetings with the Challenge Organisations** and/or the scale-ups to help them define their needs and agree on a common action plan that will be described in an MoU document.

This document will provide the basic requirements that will be needed by the scaleups to adapt or customize their solutions and products and will outline their future collaboration options: direct sale, common R&I project, pre-commercial procurements (PCPs) and public procurements of

innovative solutions (PPIs) opportunities, further work etc. The work of the Tech Brokers will start on April 1 and end on September 30, 2024.

3.3. Working as an S3E expert

Working as an expert in short.

3.3.1. Place of Work

All tasks may be carried out online or in the startup premises (if proximity allows) – note that in-person mentoring/matching is not a requirement and travel expenses are not covered by the S3E project.

3.3.2. Conflict of Interest

Experts shall **NOT** be appointed for proposals, projects, startups, or corporates if they have a vested interest that could influence their evaluation or mentoring process.

3.3.3. Confidentiality

Experts are going to be handling classified information, so they shall need to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement.

3.3.4. Remuneration

This is a volunteer programme carried out on a pro-bono basis. By participating experts indicate their understanding that they are not paid for their time, and that they do not expect anything in return (no equity, no cash, no future contract, etc.), other than the satisfaction of helping research teams or start-ups with whom they are assigned to evaluate/mentoring/match.

4 Application and Selection Process

To work as an expert assisting the S3E project, you must declare your interest by applying to the “S3E Call for Experts”. The selection results will be communicated directly to you depending on the role you choose.

4.1. Open Call Submission

All experts should fulfill the eligibility criteria as expressed below in point 4.2. and submit the application form available at <https://www.f6s.com/s3e-call-for-experts/apply>.

The key dates for the opening and closing of the call, the evaluation process and the announcement of the results are mentioned in the table below:

Call for experts	S3E Start & Charge (evaluators, mentors)	S3E Reverse (brokers)
Opening	16 October 2023 (12:00 CET)	15 November 2023 (12:00 CET)
Closing	30 November 2023 (17:00 CET)	15 January 2024 (17:00 CET)
Evaluation	1 December - 10 December 2023	15 January – 30 January 2024
Announcement	11 December 2023	1 February 2024

Table 3. Key Dates for the S3E Call #2 for Experts

4.2. Eligible Profiles

We are looking for experts with a high level of expertise and professional experience in supporting deep-tech projects, growth, and scaling startups. **Experts** are considered eligible for S3E Call for experts if they comply with **ALL** the following rules:

- High-level expertise and professional experience in supporting technological innovation, preferably in deep tech projects, growth, and scaling startups.
- Experience in the following science fields: agricultural sciences, engineering and technology, medical and health sciences, and natural sciences.
- A very good level of English is required because it is the official language of the program.
- Knowledge of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
- Experience in providing innovation support, evaluation, mentoring, and /or coaching.

4.3. Exclusion

Persons who are subject to EU administrative sanctions (i.e., exclusion or financial penalty decision) or in one of the following exclusion situations that bar them from receiving EU funds can **NOT** work as S3E experts:

- bankruptcy, winding up, court-ordered administration, arrangement with creditors, suspension of business activities or similar procedures.
- in breach of social security or tax obligations – guilty of grave professional misconduct
- committed fraud, corruption, links to a criminal organization, money laundering, terrorism-related crimes (including terrorism financing), child labor or human trafficking.
- shown significant deficiencies in complying with main obligations under an EU procurement contract, grant agreement, prize, expert contract, or similar.
- guilty of irregularities within the meaning of Article 1(2) of Regulation No 2988/95 – have created an entity under a different jurisdiction with the intent to circumvent fiscal, social, or other legal obligations in the country of origin. Experts will also be refused if it turns out that during the contract procedure, they misrepresented information required as a condition for participating or failed to supply that information – they are in a conflict of interest.

4.4. Selection

Selection of experts will be made from F6S applications by the S3E team, based on selection criteria such as professional expertise and experience, language skills, geographical and business-sector balance, gender balance, regular rotation, and absence of conflict of interest. The procedure will be objective and follow the principles of non-discrimination and equal treatment.

4.5. Experts Assignment

S3E experts will be assigned to the relevant targets based on several key factors:

- The right fit between project/startup and evaluators/mentors/brokers' expertise.
- The geographic proximity – mentors/brokers are assigned to projects/startups within their Regional/National Hub.
- Other factors include language skills, track record, sectoral expertise, and so on.

4.6. Contracting

Selected experts will sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) and Memorandum of Understanding with the details regarding their role.

5 Benefits for all Experts

In addition to benefiting from the opportunity to share your own experience and knowledge to help another colleague grow and develop, as an expert, you can also take advantage of the following opportunities:

- Play an active role in the Southern European deep tech ecosystem.
- Gain access to the S3E Network and expand your professional network.

- Connect with relevant EU institutions and stakeholders.
- Have the opportunity to 'give something back' by:
 - Providing insights into processes and practices you are familiar with.
 - Sharing good practices from your own experience.
 - Offering perspectives and insights into new or different ways of doing things.
 - Helping new colleagues hit the ground running and be as effective as possible in their roles.
- Learn by gaining exposure to new ideas, approaches, and perspectives.
- Gain recognition for your skills, experience, and your contribution as an expert, enhancing your professional profile.
- Develop valuable interpersonal and communication skills such as listening and questioning.
- **Be at the forefront of the deep tech revolution.**

6 Other Conditions

6.1. Ownership and Use of Results

The results produced in every interaction of each role (Evaluators, Mentors for deep tech projects, Mentors for deep tech growth startups, Deep tech brokers) will belong to the S3E project.

6.2. Data Protection

The personal data of experts are confidential. S3E partners will act as Data Controllers of data submitted through the F6S platform for these purposes. The F6S platform's system design and operational procedures ensure that data is managed in compliance with The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Each expert will accept the F6S terms to ensure coverage.

Please refer to <https://www.f6s.com/privacy-policy> to check the F6S platform data privacy policy and security measures and to <https://south3e.eu/privacy-policy/> to get informed about the S3E Privacy Policy.

